

UDC 342.9:343.62

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Some Aspects of Domestic Violence

Стаття присвячена окремим аспектам попередження домашнього насильства. У статті розглянуто питання юридичної відповідальності за вчинення домашнього насильства. Автор проаналізував коло осіб на яких поширюється законодавство у сфері попередження та протидії правопорушень на сімейно-побутовому ґрунті. У статті наведено окремі аспекти правового регулювання у сфері шлюбно-сімейних, родинних відносин, а також їх вплив на кваліфікацію домашнього насильства.

Ключові слова: домашнє насильство, невиконання термінового заборонного припису особою, стосовно якої він винесений, попередження домашнього насильства, адміністративна відповідальність, суб'єкт, об'єкт, суб'єктивна сторона, суб'єктивна сторона.

Статья посвящена отдельным аспектам предупреждения домашнего насилия. В статье рассмотрены вопросы юридической ответственности за совершение домашнего насилия. Автор проанализировал круг лиц, на которых распространяется законодательство в сфере предупреждения и противодействия правонарушений на семейно-бытовой почве. В статье приведены отдельные аспекты правового регулирования в сфере брачно-семейных, родственных отношений, а также их влияние на квалификацию домашнего насилия.

Ключевые слова: домашнее насилие, невыполнение срочного запретного предписания лицом, в отношении которого оно вынесено, предупреждения домашнего насилия, административная ответственность, субъект, объект, субъективная сторона, субъективная сторона.

The article is devoted to critical issues in the prevention of domestic violence. The article considers the issue of legal responsibility for committing domestic violence. The author analyzed the range of persons covered by the legislation in the field of prevention and counteraction to offenses on a family and domestic basis. The article presents some aspects of legal regulation in the fields of marital, family and family relations, as well as their impact on the qualification (threshold) of domestic violence.

The author details the composition of the administrative offense provided for in Article 173-2 Committing domestic violence, gender-based violence, non-compliance with an urgent prohibition or failure to notify place of temporary staying of the The Code of Ukraine of Administrative Offenses.

The article examines in detail the subject, object, subjective and objective side of the commission of domestic violence, for which there is administrative liability. The author analyzes the act of committing domestic violence, failure to comply with an urgent injunction by the person against whom it was issued.

The author analyzes the objective side of the administrative offense provided for in Article 173-2 of the Code of Ukraine on Administrative Offenses through the prism of types of domestic violence, namely sexual, physical, psychological and economic violence.

Special attention is paid to the fact that the provisions of Article 173-2 of the Code of Ukraine on Administrative Offenses do not cover sexual domestic violence.

Keywords: domestic violence, non-compliance with an urgent injunction by the person against whom it was issued, prevention of domestic violence, administrative liability, subject, object, subjective party, subjective party.

Addressing the problem. New challenges of the reform process in Ukraine require improvement of police response standards to offenses in general and in the field of reacting on domestic violence particular.

Analysis of research and publications. The issue of preventions and detecting various types of offenses has been the subject of research by many scientists, namely: O.Bandurka, O.Dzafarova, G.Dzgupov, A.Komzuk, N.Matuchina, O.Shatrava, and others. Peculiarities of law regulation to cases of domestic violence that contain signs of administrative offenses have been studied in the works of such national scientists as A.Baida, U.Novakovskaya A.Dominichak, E.Benkovska, L.Sukmanovska and others.

Previously unsolved problems. However, taking into account the incomplete process of improving current Ukrainian legislation in the field of prevention of domestic violence, improving legal liability for domestic violence, reforming the National Police of Ukraine, the difference in the effectiveness of police response to cases of child abuse, some aspects need further research. This determines the relevance of the study of administrative law regulations of responsibility for domestic violence.

Basic content

Consider the administrative and legal characteristics of Article 173-2 Committing domestic violence, gender-based violence, failure to comply with an urgent prohibition or failure to notify the place of his temporary stay of the Code of Ukraine on Administrative Offenses [1, c.386-387].

The subject of the offense is: general, physically sane has reached 16 years of age and is provided for in Article 3 of the Law of Ukraine "On Prevention and Counteraction to Domestic Violence"; special, a person who has already been fined for a similar offense.

According to Article 3 of the Law of Ukraine "On Prevention and Counteraction to Domestic Violence", the law applies to the following persons: spouses; ex-spouse; brides; mother (father) or child (children) of one of the spouses (former spouses); the other spouse (former spouse); who live (lived) together with one family, but are not (were not) married to each other, their parents and children; have a common child (children); parents (mother, father) and child (children); grandfather (grandmother) and grandson (granddaughter); great-grandfather (great-grandmother); great-grandson (great-

granddaughter); stepfather (stepmother) and stepson (stepdaughter); brother and sister; other relatives: uncle (aunt) and nephew (niece); cousins; cousin grandfather (grandmother) and cousin grandson (granddaughter); children of spouses, ex-spouses, brides, persons who have a common child (s) who are not common or adopted; guardians, trustees, their children and persons who are (were) under guardianship, custody; foster parents; foster parents; foster carers, their children and foster children; foster children who live (lived) in the family of a foster parent; other relatives, other persons connected by common life have mutual rights and obligations, provided they live together in accordance with Article 3 of the Law of Ukraine "On Prevention and Counteraction to Domestic Violence" [2].

Considering the range of persons covered by the legislation on the prevention and combating of domestic violence, the following should be noted. According to the Family Code of Ukraine, spouses are persons (women and men) who, on the basis of free consent, have registered their marriage in the manner prescribed by applicable law. A person who has reached the age of marriage, namely 18 years of age, may express voluntary consent to marry. According to paragraph 2 of Article 23 of the Family Code of Ukraine, the right to marry may be granted to a person who has not reached the age of majority, if he has reached 16 years of age, he went to court and the latter found that it is in her interests [3].

It is important to remember that a couple is considered a family even when the wife and husband do not live together due to education, work, treatment, the need to care for parents, children and other valid reasons. This is why it is not necessary for a couple to live together to qualify for domestic violence.

Family relationships should be understood as follows. Living together as a woman and a man without marriage and having common family rights and responsibilities (for example, maintenance, care and repair of housing, payment of utilities, running a household, namely cooking, cleaning, washing clothes, etc.). It should be remembered that a woman and man living together without marriage is not a basis for the emergence of their rights and responsibilities of spouses (Part 2 of Article 21 of the Family Code of Ukraine).

The subjective side of the offense is determined by the person's attitude to the consequences

and is characterized by the presence of guilt in the form of direct or indirect intent.

The object of this offense is public relations in the field of protection of citizens' rights [4].

The objective side of the offense under Article 173-2 of the Code of Administrative Offenses is manifested in the form:

- committing domestic violence, gender-based violence, i.e. intentionally committing any acts (actions or omissions) of a physical, psychological or economic nature (use of violence that did not cause bodily harm, threats, insults or harassment, deprivation of housing, food, clothing, other property or funds to which the victim is entitled by law, etc.), as a result of which the physical or mental health of the victim may have been or has been harmed;

- non-compliance with the urgent prohibition order by the person in respect of whom it was issued;

- failure to notify the authorized units of the National Police of Ukraine of the place of his / her temporary stay in case of his / her removal.

Let's consider the objective side of the administrative offense provided for in Article 173-2 of the Code of Administrative Offenses through the prism of types of domestic violence, namely sexual, physical, psychological and economic. It should be remembered that the provisions of Article 173-2 of the Code of Administrative Offenses do not cover sexual domestic violence.

Physical domestic violence includes such physical impact on the victim's body that did not cause bodily harm.

Psychological domestic violence can manifest, but does not end, in the form of threats, insults or harassment. This type of violence includes:

- verbal threats, including to third parties,
- humiliation,
- intimidation,
- other actions aimed at restricting the will of the person.

The consequence of such actions or omissions is the emergence of the victim's fear for their (or third parties) safety, emotional insecurity, inability to protect themselves or harm to the mental health of the person [5].

Economic violence involves the deprivation of housing, food, clothing, other property, funds or documents or the ability to use them to which the victim is entitled by law, as well as leaving him or

her unattended or incapacitated, obstructing access to necessary treatment or rehabilitation services; coercion, prohibition to study and other economic offenses [5].

Place and time of the offense. It should be remembered that the place and time of the offense does not affect the qualification of the offense, domestic violence can be committed both at the place of residence of the aggressor with the victim, and outside it (in any public or private place).

Failure to comply with the urgent injunction by the person in respect of whom it was issued implies a deliberate violation by the offender of prohibitions and / or obligations, namely: the obligation to leave the place of residence (stay) of the victim; ban on entry and stay in the place of residence (stay) of the victim; prohibition in any way to contact the victim [6].

The refusal of the offender to leave the place of residence (stay) of the victim is an administrative offense with a formal composition.

Socially dangerous consequences of domestic violence are covered by the provisions of Art. 173-2 of the Code of Administrative Offenses, and is seen in the possibility of occurrence (but not actual occurrence) of any harm to the physical or mental health of the victim.

The sanction of the article provides for the imposition of a fine of 10 to 20 non-taxable minimum incomes or community service for a period of 30 to 40 hours, or administrative arrest for up to 7 days. Qualifying signs of the offense under Article 173-2 of the Code of Administrative Offenses are the commission of repeated acts under this article during the year.

In accordance with Part 2 of Art. 173-2 of the Code of Administrative Offenses, the above actions committed by a person who during the year was subjected to an administrative penalty for one of the violations under Part 1 of Article 173-2 entail a fine of 20 to 40 tax-free minimum incomes or community service for a period of 40 to 60 hours, or administrative arrest for up to 15 days.

It should be noted that the offender may be prosecuted for other illegal acts, namely:

- bringing a minor intoxicated by his parents or persons replacing them (Article 180 of the Code of Administrative Offenses);

- failure of parents or persons replacing them to fulfill their responsibilities for the upbringing of

children (Article 184 of the Code of Administrative Offenses);

- engaging in prostitution (Article 181-1 of the Code of Administrative Offenses);

- manufacture, storage of moonshine and devices for its production (Article 176 of the Code of Administrative Offenses);

- purchase of moonshine and other strong home-made spirits (Article 177 of the Code of Administrative Offenses), etc.

Thus, the international community pays considerable attention to preventing and combating

gender-based violence, including domestic violence. Ukraine, as a legal, democratic, social state, has joined a number of international treaties, including the Council of Europe Decision № 210 “On Preventing and Combating Violence against Women and Domestic Violence”. In pursuance of the provisions of these international agreements, the legislator has provided for administrative and criminal liability for domestic violence.

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